

Paper Chromatographic Separation of Isomeric Thioureas, Thiazoles and Thiazolines from One Another

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Paper chromatographic separation of isomeric mono aryl thioureas like *p*-carboxy phenyl thiourea from *o*-carboxy phenyl thiourea and *o*-carboxy phenyl thiourea from *m*-carboxy phenyl thiourea, isomeric sym-diaryl thioureas like sym-di (*o*-carboxy phenyl) thiourea from sym-di-*p*-carboxy phenyl thiourea, isomeric thiazoles like 4-phenyl-2-*o*-carboxy phenyl amino thiazole from 4 phenyl 2-*p*-carboxy phenylamino thiazole and 4 methyl 2-*o*-carboxy phenyl amino thiazole from 4-methyl 2-*p*-carboxy phenyl amino thiazole; isomeric thiazolines like 4-phenyl 2-*o*-carboxy phenyl imino-3-*o*-carboxy phenyl Δ^4 -thiazoline from 4-phenyl 2-*p*-carboxy phenyl imino-3-*p*-carboxy phenyl Δ^4 -thiazoline and 4-methyl-2-*p*-chlorophenyl imino 3-*p*-chlorophenyl Δ^4 -thiazoline from 4-methyl-2-*m*-chlorophenyl imino-3-*m*-chlorophenyl Δ^4 -thiazoline has been effected successfully in various solvent systems.

During the investigation of the condensation of unsaturated¹ and saturated ketones² on mono aryl and sym-diaryl thioureas³ in presence of bromine and iodine separately, it was necessary to study the separation and identification of final products and the optimum conditions for their maximum yield. Paper chromatography which has shown wide applicability in recent years was suggested to be a suitable technique for this purpose.

Hundreds of organic and inorganic compounds have been separated by this technique, but separation of very few sulphur containing heterocyclic compounds have been reported. Paper chromatographic studies on sulphonamides⁴, diazotized sulphanilic acids⁵, aliphatic sulphonic acids⁶, alkyl sulphates⁷, ureas, methyl ureas⁸, thioureas, biuret derivatives, isothiourium bases⁹ and acetylated thioureas¹⁰, in various solvent systems are found in literature to certain extent, but no such work on heterocyclic compounds containing sulphur like thiazoles, thiazolines or thiazolidines or even mono or diaryl substituted thioureas have been reported. So it was considered worthwhile to undertake the paper chromatographic studies of these sulphur containing heterocyclic compounds and thioureas with a view to separate them from one another effectively. During the investigations, it was evident that it is not only possible to separate thiazoles from the corresponding thioureas, but it is also possible to separate isomeric thioureas, thiazoles and thiazolines from one another.

A large number of solvent systems^{11,12,13} were tried for these separations, out of which a few gave promising results, as is evident from their R_f values given in Table 1.

Of the isomeric mono aryl thioureas, *o*-carboxy phenyl thiourea and *p*-carboxy phenyl thiourea could be completely separated from their mixture in any of the eleven solvent systems used but for the separation of *o*-carboxyphenyl thiourea from *m*-carboxy phenyl thiourea, solvents A, B, C, D, E & F are the solvents of choice as is evident from the R_f values in Table 1. The spots were round and well separated from one another in all the cases.

Five other binary mixtures of isomeric diaryl thioureas, thiazoles and thiazolines viz. (a) sym-di(*o*-carboxyphenyl)thiourea and sym.di(*p*-carboxy phenyl) thiourea in solvents A, B, E, I, J, K; (b) 2-(*o*-carboxyphenyl amino)-4-methyl-thiazole and 2-(*p*-carboxyphenyl amino) 4-methyl thiazole in solvents J & K; (c) 2-(*o*-carboxy phenyl amino)4- phenyl thiazole and 2(*p*-carboxy phenyl amino)-4-phenyl thiazole in solvent E; (d) 2-*m*-chlorophenyl imino-3-*m*-chlorophenyl-4-methyl- Δ^4 -thiazoline and 2-(*p*-chloro phenyl imino)-3-*p*-chlorophenyl-4-methyl- Δ^4 -thiazoline; (e) 2-(*o*-carboxyphenyl imino)-3-*o*-carboxy phenyl-4-phenyl Δ^4 -thiazoline and 2 (*p*-carboxy phenyl imino)-3-*p*-carboxy phenyl-4-phenyl- Δ^4 -thiazoline in solvents, I, J & K were chromatographed similarly. They were successfully separated from one another as evident from their R_f , values which are quite apart in the respective solvent systems as given in Table 1.

EXPERIMENTAL

Strips of Whatman No. 1 chromatographic papers (80 cm \times 15 cm) were used for chromatography. On each paper strip 5 μ litres of the saturated solutions of two of the samples to be separated along with their equimolecular mixture were spotted on three different points 5 cm. apart on a straight line 10 cm. away from one of the short edges. Care had been taken to keep the diameter of the spots within 5 mm.

The papers were developed in rectangular chambers already saturated with the developing solvent and were developed by descending technique. The developing time period was 7–14 hrs differing from solvent to solvent.

After the development was over, the papers were taken out from the chamber and were air dried. The spots were visualized by spraying the paper with the following reagents¹⁴:

- (a) Feigl's reagent followed by starch solution in case of mono aryl thioureas—colourless well defined round spots well separated from one another on a bluish background were obtained.
- (b) Tollens' reagent in case of sym-di aryl thioureas—grey spot against a colourless background was observed.
- (c) 5% Na_2CO_3 solution followed by freshly prepared diazotized sulphanilic acid solution for thiazoles—clear orange-red, round, well separated spots on whitish background were obtained.
- (d) 0.5% solution of acidified KMnO_4 solution in case of thiazolines—nice circular well separated colorless spots were obtained against a pink background.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Name of the compounds	R _f values in different solvent systems											
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	
1.	<i>p</i> -carboxy phenyl thiourea	.55	.21	.09	.02	.02	.25	.42	.36	.59	.08	.44	
2.	<i>o</i> -carboxy phenyl thiourea	.70	.64	.74	.59	.52	.81	.82	.80	.85	.72	.72	
3.	<i>m</i> -carboxy phenyl thiourea	.54	.15	.08	.02	.02	.24	—	—	—	—	—	
4.	Sym-di(<i>o</i> -carboxy phenyl) thiourea.	.91	.78	—	—	.78	—	—	—	.85	.78	.71	
5.	Sym-di(<i>p</i> -carboxy phenyl) thiourea.	.64	.18	—	—	.028	—	—	—	.61	.04	.35	
6.	4-phenyl-2-(<i>p</i> -carboxy phenyl) amino thiazole.	—	—	—	—	.85	—	—	—	—	—	—	
7.	4-phenyl-2-(<i>o</i> -carboxy phenyl) amino thiazole.	—	—	—	—	.65	—	—	—	—	—	—	
8.	4-methyl 2-(<i>p</i> -carboxy phenyl) amino thiazole	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	.18	.39	
9.	4-methyl-2-(<i>o</i> -carboxy phenyl) amino thiazole.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	.82	.88	
10.	4-phenyl-2- <i>o</i> -carboxyphenyl imino-3- <i>o</i> -carboxy phenyl Δ ⁴ -thiazoline.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	.92	.97	.95	
11.	4-phenyl-2- <i>p</i> -carboxy phenyl imino-3- <i>p</i> -carboxy phenyl Δ ⁴ -thiazoline.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	.48	.32	.62	
12.	4-methyl-2- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl imino-3- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl Δ ⁴ -thiazoline.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	.88	.90	.87	
13.	4-methyl-2- <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl- imino-3- <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl Δ ⁴ -thiazoline.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	.56	.60	.58	
Duration of run		6hr.	7hr.	5hr.	11hr.	12hr.	12hr.	10hr.	11hr.	11hr.	10hr.	11hr.	
Solvent A — Petr. Ether : (boiling range 60°–80°)—Methanol								(70 : 30 V/V)					
,, B — Petr. Ether : (,,)—Acetone								(50 : 50 ,,)					
,, C — Petr. Ether : (,,)—Ethanol								(50 : 50 ,,)					
,, D — Petr. Ether : (,,)—N-Propanol								(50 : 50 ,,)					
,, E — N-Butanol : Isopropanol								(50 : 50 ,,)					
,, F — Benzene : Ethanol								(50 : 50 ,,)					
,, G — Isopropanol : Ether								(20 : 80 ,,)					
,, H — Abs. Alcohol : Ether								(50 : 50 ,,)					
,, I — Benzene : Methanol								(50 : 50 ,,)					
,, J — Benzene : N-Propanol								(50 : 50 ,,)					
,, K — Benzene : Ethanol								(50 : 50 ,,)					

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